

Study of the Antagonistic Effect of Bacteria Isolated from the Left and Right Wings of Houseflies

Zahraa Abdalameer
Environmental Health Department, College of Environmental Sciences,
Al-Qasim Green University, Babylon 51013, Iraq

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Abstract

Sixty houseflies (*Musca domestica*) were collected from the city of Hilla and from different locations (Al-Karama, Al-Akramin) between February and March 2025. The highest number of bacteria isolated from the fly's body was found at 5.60×10^3 colonies/cm³, compared to 2.5×10^3 and 3.42×10^3 , respectively, on the right and left wings. The following bacteria were isolated from the right wing: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella*, *Klebsiella*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*. From the left wing, only three types of bacteria were isolated: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella*. A type of yeast, *Saccharomyces servishiae*, was also isolated. The bacteria isolated from both wings (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) showed heterogeneous antimicrobial activity against isolates from the same wing and the opposite wing. Similarly, the two isolates belonging to *Klebsiella* and *Shigella* showed activity against most of the species studied.

Keywords: *Musca domestica*, bacteria, public health, symbiotic relationship.

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Introduction

Insects in general, and flies in particular, have a clear impact on human public health. Research into insect-associated microbes is considered an exciting field of study, as the relationship between microbes and insects may be a phoresy relationship or a symbiotic relationship. The role of insect-associated microbes in disease transmission or food spoilage has been studied by many scientists (Greenberg (1982), Aleanos and Frishman (1980), and (Meoay *et al.* (1982).

Other scientists have discussed the symbiotic relationship between microbes and different types of insects, such as Breznak (1982), who recorded more than 100 types of pathogens transmitted by houseflies, including 3 types of

viruses, 41 types of bacteria, 5 types of protozoa, 7 types of tapeworms, and 14 types of fungi.

There are about 60 species belonging to the *Musca* genus of flies, which are widespread and associated with humans. They are found inside and outside buildings on fruits, vegetables, and drinks, and are a source of annoyance to humans and animals and a carrier of many serious diseases. Among them is the housefly, *Musca domestica*, which carries an arsenal of vital weapons and belongs to the Muscidae family of the Diptera order (Al-Hajj Ismail and others, 2009). Flies frequent dirt, animal waste, stables, and poultry farms, as their larvae live in those materials. There are many types of flies that transmit numerous diseases, including the black fly, which transmits leishmaniasis; the sand fly,

which transmits cutaneous leishmaniasis; the horsefly, which transmits the bacteria that cause anthrax and possibly HIV; the tsetse fly, which transmits the deadly sleeping sickness; and the housefly, which, by moving between feces and food, becomes an ideal vector for many deadly diseases that affect humans, including polio. (Al-Hajj Ismail et al., 2009; Cranshaw and Pearis, 2009)

There is a characteristic in one of the wings of the housefly that it carries the disease and the cure in its wings. If the fly falls into the food or drink and throws the germs stuck to it, then the closest pesticide for those germs is the pesticide that the fly carries in its body near one of its wings. So, if there is a disease, then its cure is close to it. Therefore, dipping the whole fly and throwing it is enough to kill the germs that were stuck to it. It has also been scientifically proven that the fly carries the bacteriophage that kills bacteria (Shope, 1927).

The current research aims to isolate the different types of germs found on the wings of the housefly (*Musca domestica*) and investigate their ability to produce antibacterial substances isolated from the fly's wings, as well as to identify the disease and the cure in the wings of the housefly, in accordance with the hadith of the Messenger (may God bless him and his family and grant them peace): "If a fly falls into the vessel of one of you, let him dip it in and then throw it away, for in one of its wings is a disease and in the other is a cure." This is one of the authentic hadiths, as narrated by many narrators.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Flies

60 houseflies (*Musca domestica*) were collected from the city of Hilla and from different areas during the period of February-

March 2025. The insects were transported in sterile tubes to the laboratory for dissection and isolation of microorganisms.

Dissection of Flies

Separate the right and left wings from the fly's body using sterile micro-dissection instruments. Place the right and left wings and the body separately in 5 cm³ of sterile 0.9% natural solution (Hassan, 2008).

Bacteria Analysis

0.05 cm³ was taken from a sample (right wing, left wing, and body of the fly) and spread on the following culture media: Nutrient Agar, Blood Agar, MacConkey Agar, EMB medium, and Manetol salt Agar. It was incubated aerobically at 37°C. The number of bacteria (colony-forming units, CFU) was counted after 48 hours. The isolated bacterial samples were purified and stored on nutrient broth medium for use in experiments. The species were identified based on Winn et al. (2006), Collee *et al.* (1996), and Holt *et al.* (1994).

Antimicrobial Activity

This was done using the Waksman (1967) method modified by Al-Samak (2006) to study the antimicrobial activity of different types of bacteria on the right wing against types of bacteria on the left wing and vice versa.

Results and Discussion

The results in Table 1 show a high numerical density and diversity of microorganisms present on the wings of the housefly *Musca domestica*, especially bacteria, as shown in Table 1, since the microbial diversity on the wings of flies, as well as the numerical density, reflects the environment in which they live (Butler *et al.*, 2010).

Table 1. Number of Bacterial Colonies (CFU/ 1cm³) Isolated from Houseflies *Musca domestica*

Number of bacterial colonies CFU / cm ³ × 10 ³			Culture media	Number of samples
Left wing	Right wing	body		
3.420 – 0	2.500 – 0	5.600 – 0	Nutrient agar	60
4.500 – 0	4.320 – 0	5.720 – 0	McConkey agar	

Table (2) shows the most important bacterial species isolated from both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria from both the right and left wings. From the right wing, the following bacterial species were obtained: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella*, *Klebsiella*, *Alternaria alternate*, *Aspergillus fumigates*.

On the left wing, the following species were obtained: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella*.

Table 2. The most Important Microscopic Species Isolated from the Wings of the Housefly

Isolated microorganisms	
Right wing	Left wing
Proteus vulgaris	Pseudomonas aeruginosa
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Staphylococcus aureus
Staphylococcus aureus	Klebsiella
Shigella	
Klebsiella	
Escherichia coli	
Aspergillus fumigates	
Alternaria alternata	

The bacterial isolates growing on the wings of flies were distinguished by their particular medical importance in their ability to transmit many diseases that affect the systems of humans, animals, and plants, as well as food spoilage, etc.,

as indicated by (Yap *et al.*, 2008; Yousef, 2008), as the isolated species are considered important pathogens.

If we return to the text of the Prophet's hadith, may God bless him and grant him peace, regarding the order to dip flies, the mechanism of secreting the active substance (medicine) becomes clear. The effectiveness of beneficial bacteria and fungi is only achieved in the presence of the food or drink medium inside the container. This medium allows for the interaction of both the disease and the medicine. At that point, the beneficial organisms eliminate the harmful organisms. It was also found that the antibacterial substance that kills bacteria is only released if it absorbs the liquid, and with the presence of osmotic pressure, it will swell, burst, and release its toxins to eliminate the harmful bacteria.

Table 3 illustrates the effect of the antimicrobial activity of bacterial species isolated from the left wing on bacteria isolated from the right wing. The results show that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from the left wing exhibited good antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Klebsiella* due to its high capacity for producing antibiotics. *Staphylococcus aureus* did not affect any of the bacterial species, while *Klebsiella* showed a clear effect on *Proteus vulgaris* and no effect on the other species.

Table 3. The Effect of the Antimicrobial Activity of the Bacterial Species Isolated from the Left Wing on the Bacteria Isolated from the Right Wing

Right wing	Left wing	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>Staphylococcus Aureus</i>
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>		-	+	-
<i>Klebsiella</i>		+	-	-
<i>Shigella</i>		-	-	-
<i>Escherichia coli</i>		+	-	-
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>		+	+	-

Note: + Good effect; - no effect.

Table 4. The Effect of the Antagonistic Activity of the Bacterial Species Isolated from the Right Wing on the Left Wing

Left wing	Right wing	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>Shigella</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>		-	-	-	-	-	-

<i>Klebsiella</i>	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-

Note: + Good effect; - no effect.

Given the importance of *Pseudomonas* bacteria isolated from both wings in terms of their production of the antibiotic pyocynin, its effect on bacteria isolated from the same wing was studied, as shown in Table 5.

The species showed efficiency in inhibiting the affiliated isolates (*Klebsiella*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Escherichia coli*).

Table 5. Effect of the Antagonistic Activity of the Isolate Belonging to the Species (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) Isolated from the Right Wing on the Bacterial Species Isolated from the Same Wing

Right wing	<i>Pseudomona aeruginosa</i>
<i>Klebsiella</i>	+
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	+
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+
<i>Shigella</i>	-

A

B

C

D

E

Figure 1. A) and B) illustrate the inhibitory effect of *Pseudomonas* bacteria on *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, respectively. C) illustrates the inhibitory effect of *Klebsiella* bacteria on *Pseudomonas* bacteria. D) and E) illustrate the inhibitory effect of both *Klebsiella* and *Shigella* bacteria on *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria

Conclusion

Most pathogenic bacteria were isolated from the wings of the housefly, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella*, *Klebsiella*, *Alternaria alternata*, and *Aspergillus fumigatus*.

Some types of bacteria, especially *Pseudomonas*, can secrete an antimicrobial substance called (pyocynine), which inhibits the growth of other bacterial species.

It was concluded that one wing of the fly carries the disease, while the other carries the cure.

Recommendations

- 1) Isolating microorganisms from other types of insects of medical importance.
- 2) Studying medical insects at molecular and genetic levels.
- 3) Studying insects related to forensic evidence and their relationship to microbes.
- 4) Studying the effects of substances produced by insects to determine their inhibitory effect on the growth of pathogenic microorganisms and vice versa.

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